

5-Acetamino-2-methylacetophenone: *p*-Toluidine (10 g) converted into its acetotoluidide was heated with PPA (H_3PO_4 , 40 ml; P_2O_5 , 48 g) at 160° for 5 h. After treating the reaction mixture with ice-water, the filtrate (800 ml) on keeping overnight in a freezer gave a solid and crystallised from ethanol, (5.5 g, 50.8%), m.p. 124° (Found: N, 7.41. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2$ calcd.: N, 7.32%); it could not be cyclised with PPA or Na-acetate and Ac_2O ; its oxime, m.p. $146-47^\circ$ (Found: N, 13.10. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_2$ calcd.: N, 13.17%).

6-Acetamino-3-methylacetophenone: *p*-Toluidine, converted into its acetotoluidide was heated with PPA (H_3PO_4 , 36 ml; P_2O_5 , 36 g) at 160° for 5 h. The turbid solution obtained after treating the reaction mass with cold water and on further cooling with ice gave a product, which was crystallised from ethanol, (2.2 g, 12%), m.p. 105° (Found: N, 7.10. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2$ calcd.: N, 7.32%). It gave tests with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine. Kohler⁴ obtained a ketone (m.p. 105°) heating aceto-*p*-toluidide with acetic acid and syrupy phosphoric acid.

Ir spectra: 2,6-Dimethyl-4-hydroxyquinoline exists in tautomeric forms. Its ir spectra in solid state show band at 1665 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=O stretch which does not appear with its 4-chloro derivative; a weak band at 3270 cm^{-1} due to NH stretch in keto form; and medium bands at 2865 , 2935 and 3040 cm^{-1} due to C—H stretch, CH_3 group and ring CH, respectively.

For its chloro-compound, medium bands at 2860 , 2980 and 3040 cm^{-1} are due to C—H stretch, CH_3 groups and ring CH stretching, respectively. The C—H out-of-plane deformation in the chloroderivative is only due to one free H-atom in one ring, which absorbs very strongly at 831 cm^{-1} , corresponding to *p*-substituted aromatics. In addition, both show a second weak band at $900-850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be associated with vibration of remaining ring H-atoms.

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References

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Preparation of 2,4-Benzylidene-L-xylose

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It was found by Malaprade that organic compounds containing two hydroxyl groups attached to two adjacent carbon atoms undergo a cleavage of the carbon-carbon bond when oxidised by sodium metaperiodate¹. Another oxidising reagent which can be used is Criegee's reagent or lead tetraacetate². But in the case of carbohydrates and their derivatives sodium metaperiodate is more efficient because it is more quantitative and the yields are comparatively superior^{3,4}.

2,4-Benzylidene-D-sorbitol was prepared by the method of von Vargha⁵, and it was then subjected to oxidative degradation with sodium metaperiodate to give 2,4-benzylidene-L-xylose (1).

Compound 1 is a starting material for the synthesis of ascorbic acid or vitamin C. This reaction can be used on a commercial scale.

Experimental

Oxidative degradation of 2,4-benzylidene-D-sorbitol to 2,4-benzylidene-L-xylose. 2,4-Benzylidene-D-sorbitol (100 g) was reacted with a solution of sodium metaperiodate (90 g) in water (1900 ml). The slight excess of sodium metaperiodate was removed with drops of glycerol. The solution was stirred for 1.5 h. It was then evaporated to a smaller volume. The resulting product was extracted with hot ethyl acetate. The extract was washed with water, dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate, and then ethyl acetate was evaporated to yield 2,4-benzylidene-L-xylose (80 g), m.p. 162° (Found: C, 43.40; H, 8.52. $C_{12}H_{14}O_5$ calcd. for: C, 43.37; H, 8.43%), $[\alpha]_D^{25} 4.4^\circ$.

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